

POLICY BRIEF COMMON TEMPLATE

RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

INTRODUCTION: PROJECT TITLE AND PROJECT OBJECTIVES

CALL: Horizon 2020 - INFRAIA-02-2020

TOPIC: INTEGRATING ACTIVITIES FOR STARTING COMMUNITIES

PROJECT: Building Collaborative Urban Drainage research lab communities (Co-UDlabs).

<https://co-udlabs.eu/>

The main objective of Co-UDlabs was to provide a transnational, multidisciplinary collaborative research infrastructure. This infrastructure enables stakeholders, academic researchers, and innovators in the urban drainage sector to come together, share ideas, and co-produce project concepts. Participants then benefit from access to top-class research facilities to develop, refine, and demonstrate those concepts — ultimately fostering a collaborative European innovation community in urban drainage.

In relation with the main objective, Co-UDlabs addressed the following specific objectives:

- Foster a culture of co-operation between research infrastructures (RIs) owners and the urban drainage community through a set of coordinated Networking Activities which help to develop a more inclusive, open and efficient research and innovation environment.
- Facilitate free of charge Transnational Access to 17 leading European facilities from 7 RIs by three open calls. The calls and the project both focus on supporting both scientific communities, water utilities, and industries to offer chain innovators low threshold, well facilitated, access to highly relevant research facilities.
- Enlarge and strengthen the quality and quantity of the research, development and innovation services relating to Urban Drainage, offered at European level through a combination of interconnected Joint Research Activities, actively participating at international level.

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Co-UDlabs
COLLABORATIVE URBAN DRAINAGE
RESEARCH LAB COMMUNITIES

Deltares

eawag
aquatic research

INSA
INSTITUT NATIONAL
DE RECHERCHES
EN SANTE

graie

euronovia

IMPLEMENTATION OF RIs

During its implementation, Co-UDlabs has successfully established itself as the first distributed Research Infrastructures in the field of urban water systems, enabling access for 227 researchers from 26 countries and 122 institutions worldwide. Given that Co-UDlabs originated from the Starting Communities initiative under the H2020 INFRAIA programme, this achievement marks a significant success. The project brought together its consortium partners for the first time to create these RIs from the ground up.

However, key challenges remain in the path toward full implementation. The most pressing issues are related to i) long-term sustainability of the infrastructures and ii) harmonisation of methodologies and format of data generated across the 31 Transnational Access (TA) projects and the Joint Research Activities (JRAs), as addressed in project [Deliverable 1.3](#), [Deliverable 2.1](#), and [Deliverable 2.2](#) available in the Co-UDlabs community on Zenodo.

To better support small and medium-sized distributed RIs like Co-UDlabs, a shift in EU policy is needed. The current INFRA programme prioritises support for well-established infrastructures within the ESFRI (European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures) and ERIC (European Research Infrastructure Consortium) frameworks. This approach overlooks the essential role of Distributed Research Infrastructures (DRIs), which represent the majority of RIs in Europe and are often embedded in academic and applied research communities. The development of i) inclusive funding mechanisms, and ii) valuable services provided by emerging infrastructures such as Co-UDlabs, risk disappearing from the European Research Area, as their sustainability heavily depends on continued EU support.

ACCESS TO RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

The Co-UDlabs Transnational Access programme has significantly contributed to broader and more effective access to Research Infrastructures in the urban drainage sector. Notably, among the 227 users, 24% were women, 29% came from non-EU countries, and 33% represented non-academic institutions, demonstrating a strong outreach to underrepresented groups and sectors. The participation of users from CEE (Central and Eastern Europe) member states was low (2 countries) although in terms of Widening countries Co-UDlabs TA programme engaged institutions from 6 countries. The programme fostered interdisciplinary collaboration, with many user groups combining academic and industrial partners, and supported both early-career and senior researchers.

This diversity has enhanced the intersectoral and international reach of the infrastructures, promoting innovation in monitoring, digital water analysis, and sustainable drainage. Beyond the metrics set, the TA programme generated true but non directly quantifiable benefits such as:

- Strengthening professional networks.
- Stimulating new research ideas.
- Clarifying real-world needs through user feedback.
- Encouraging co-production of knowledge between academia and practitioners.

The impact beyond the project is being sustained through initiatives like the UDRAIN Working Group (within the [JCUD - IWA/IAHR Joint Committee on Urban Drainage](#), gathering the global international urban drainage community), which aims to create a global network of large-scale urban drainage RIs. UDRAIN is developing a worldwide Atlas of RIs, promoting standardization, data sharing, open science, and facilitating continued transnational access and collaboration.

TA programmes are a cornerstone of scientific excellence and innovation, particularly for DRIs. To maximise the impact of Co-UDlabs and similar initiatives, future EU programmes should enhance support for underrepresented regions. Greater engagement with industry and utilities is also needed, through co-designed projects and targeted training. Finally, promoting multilingual dissemination and training materials would help overcome language barriers and improve access for practitioners across Europe and beyond.

INTERACTION OF RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES WITH INDUSTRY

Several TA projects were co-developed with industry partners, such as the [AIR project](#), which brought together utilities, umbrella organizations (e.g., Stichting RIONED), and inspection technology providers to evaluate defect detection methods in wastewater pressure pipes. This collaboration not

only addressed a truly operational challenge but also created a feedback loop for product improvement, reducing innovation risks for SMEs and accelerating market uptake (more details are provided in [Deliverable 1.3](#)). Beyond direct access, Co-UDlabs supported industry through i) training and workshops tailored to practitioners, ii) hackathons and webinars that facilitated idea exchange and early-stage collaboration, and iii) dissemination of results via open-access platforms, increasing visibility and reusability of industrially relevant data.

To strengthen industry collaboration, research infrastructures should embed dedicated engagement strategies, including co-design of services, practitioner-focused training, and open innovation platforms that connect researchers with industrial users. These approaches help reduce innovation risks, accelerate technology uptake, and ensure that infrastructure services align with real-world industrial needs.

LEVEL OF CONNECTION TO EOSC

Co-UDlabs has taken initial steps toward EOSC (European Open Science Cloud) alignment by using Zenodo for open-access documents, data sets, methods, software tools and source codes sharing, ensuring visibility within the EOSC ecosystem. However, the project lacks standardized metadata, consistent ontologies, and integration with the EOSC Marketplace, limiting data discoverability and reuse. Efforts like controlled vocabularies and ontology development are ongoing but not yet fully implemented.

For further improvement, Co-UDlabs should focus on machine-actionable DMPs (Data Management Plans), adopt recognized data models, and provide better training for researchers in these practices. While tools like Renku and SensorThings API (Application Programming Interface) show promise, their use remains still limited in the urban drainage community. Stronger coordination with EOSC policies and community standards is needed to fully realize i) FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) and interoperable data sharing and ii) common research standards, methods and procedures.

SUSTAINABILITY OF RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

The long-term sustainability of the Co-UDlabs research infrastructures is a pressing concern as the project moves beyond the Horizon 2020 INFRAIA Starting Communities framework. While Co-UDlabs successfully integrated 7 RIs across Europe and built a new collaborative ecosystem for urban drainage research, the current Horizon Europe programme no longer supports the progression of such initiatives into “Advanced Communities.” Moreover, access to future funding is now largely restricted to infrastructures affiliated with ESFRI or ERIC, which excludes many distributed and mid-scale RIs like Co-UDlabs that have demonstrated strong impact but lack formal recognition within these frameworks. A further challenge is that many large RIs are owned or managed by universities and research institutions that are increasingly affected by financial constraints. Without continued EU-level support, there is a real risk that such critical infrastructures — despite their proven value — may be lost due to lack of sustainable long-term funding mechanisms.

To address these issues, Co-UDlabs will explore its integration into the ENVRI (Environmental Research Infrastructures) community, which represents environmental research infrastructures across Europe. Currently, there is no dedicated RI within ENVRI focused on the built environment or urban drainage, highlighting a critical gap that Co-UDlabs could help fill. This strategic alignment would support long-term sustainability by embedding Co-UDlabs within a broader, interdisciplinary research ecosystem. More detailed analysis and pathways are outlined in Deliverable 1.3.

The key sustainability challenge remains the absence of dedicated EU support for distributed, emerging RIs that fall outside the ESFRI/ERIC frameworks. These small to medium size infrastructures are often the most agile and responsive to sectoral needs, yet they risk disappearing without continued access to TA funding and operational support. Co-UDlabs recommends that the EU reintroduces or adapts its funding instruments to support such communities, particularly those that have demonstrated excellence and impact under the Starting Communities or Advances Community model.

In conclusion, while Co-UDlabs made significant strides in building a sustainable RI network, its future strongly depends on the EU’s willingness to recognize and support the unique value of distributed, mid-scale research infrastructures. Without this, the services, data, and collaborative platforms developed through Co-UDlabs risk being lost, undermining progress toward a more resilient and innovative European Research Area.